

Press and Public Pressure in Foreign Affairs: The Case of Political Narratives in Newspapers and their extent to influence British and Austro–Hungarian Foreign Policy decision-making in the Great Eastern Crisis of 1875–1878¹

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Abstract

Political journals of the Great Powers and their audience were greatly interested in following the prelude of the Great Eastern Crisis and its climax, the Russo–Turkish War of 1877–1878. Two Empires outside the conflict especially considered Russian defeat a favourable outcome: Austria–Hungary and Britain. Anti-Russian and pro-Turkish sentiments were prominent within the bellicose agitations, that had shaken the domestic and external front of politics in both countries. While the legislative background of the press was vastly different in the two empires, the articles discussing the events of the war show a striking resemblance. Public opinion followed these narratives and manifested on the domestic frontier: by the autumn of 1876, thousands protested on the streets of Budapest, while similarly the followers of Gladstone and the opposing ‘jingoists’ took the streets of London and other cities. Using the theory of Edward Herman and Noam Chomsky (Manufactured Consent), and the conceptual framework of Foreign Policy Analysis, I hypothesise that while the Conservative British political elite could easily frame and amplify ideas by outlets like The Daily Telegraph, Daily News, Pall Mall Gazette, and The Times, Hungarian daily papers (Pesti Napló, Hon, Ellenőr, Egyetértés) could have adopted the oven-ready narrative to express and support their pro-Turkish/anti-Russian standpoint. The aim of this paper, therefore, is to observe the parallels between British and Hungarian political press, the adaptation of news and subsequently the reception by Hungarian newsreaders. Additionally, the paper is centred around the greater issue of public pressure on foreign policy decision-making. The paper aims to examine how the narrative of the British bellicose media was adopted in leading Hungarian newspapers, and how it was received and if it formulated domestic and foreign political frontiers.

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Introduction and context

After the international sensation of the 1870–1871 Franco–Prussian war and the subsequent German unification, a cholera epidemic (1872), a stock market crash (1873) and an economic crisis in its wake shook the European Great Powers. The 1875 uprising of Herzegovinian Slavic subjects of the Ottoman Empire happened partly as a result of the aforementioned crisis, but also because of the idea of ‘another’ unification war for the Pan-Slavic cause, after the Italian (1859-1861, 1871) and German (1866, 1870-1871) historical events. In the autumn of 1874, the Slavic Christian subjects of Herzegovina were incited by their local leaders to take up arms, and later in 1875, they asked semi-independent vassals of the Ottoman Empire such as Montenegro and Serbia to aid their cause.² In a matter of weeks, the conflict escalated into an international crisis and then determined the international affairs and media agenda of the Great Powers for almost three years, to be peacefully settled by the Berlin Congress of 1878. As an ally to the Pan-Slavic cause, Russia saw the opportunity in the conflict. After the 1856 Paris Treaty, Russian decision-makers strived to end the isolation of the country. By 1871, they had partly succeeded as the Treaty of London revised the Black Seas clauses of the treaty, and it revoked the neutral status of the Black Sea.³ In the years 1875–1876, Russian leadership wanted to get similar guarantees to divide the sphere of influence in the Balkans. In the spirit of the already existing alliance between Germany, Austria-Hungary and Russia – named as League of the Three Emperors (1873) – the Reichstadt Agreement (July 8, 1876) and later the Budapest Convention (January 15, 1877) were made in secret.⁴ In the case of a Turkish victory against their Slavic subjects, the former treaty proposed a *status quo ante bellum*. If the outcome of the

² *Balkán kronológia I. Birodalmak szorításában, 1700–1878*, ed. Demeter, Gábor (Budapest–Sofia: Institut za Istoricheski Izsledvaniya, BAN, Bölcsészettudományi Kutatóközpont, Történettudományi Intézet, 2020), 197-199.

³ France-Roy Bridge and Roger Bullen, *The Great Powers and the European States System 1814–1914* (Harlow: Pearson Education, 2005), 174-177.

⁴ István Diószegi, *Bismarck és Andrássy. Magyarország a német hatalmi politikában a 19. század második felében* (Budapest, Vienna, München: Teleki Laszlo Stiftung, 1998), 205-212.

conflict would have favoured the insurgents, however, the Balkans would have been divided to a Western and Eastern sphere, accordingly to Austro-Hungarian and Russian interests, therefore avoiding direct conflict between the two Eastern powers. The Budapest Convention further reinforced the resolutions of the Reichstadt Treaty, and amended it with the prohibition of creating a large Slavic state.⁵ Despite all the precautions by the Austro-Hungarian diplomacy, as the talks at the 1876-1877 Constantinople Conference collapsed and Serbia was involved in the conflict, Tsar Alexander II saw military intervention fit, and the Russo-Turkish war came to reality on April 24, 1877.

During the crisis, the policy and international goals of Austria-Hungary were formulated by various levels of domestic actors and interests. At first glance, the Emperor and his minister of foreign affairs, Count Gyula Andrassy, along with the Viennese military circles were not interested in an anti-Russian political scheme and Andrassy gave his support to the Three Emperor's League.⁶ His former aides and the Hungarian political elite, however, did not see the political wisdom behind the alliance, nor did they accept even the slightest cooperation with a power supporting Slavic interests. In fear of losing the integrity of their multiethnic Kingdom, and because of the failure of the Hungarian revolution in 1849 – which was put down by Russian arms – the Hungarian elite strived to avoid the inclusion of even more Slavic-populated territories in the Dual Monarchy. The modern Hungarian political identity and attitude were therefore characterised by anti-Russian, and pro-Turkish sentiments.⁷ As a result of the Hungarian attitude, Andrassy had to find a way to follow the Emperor's policy, maintain the trust of his advisors, and appease or at least tone down the critical voices as much as in Hungary

⁵ Bridge and Bullen, *The Great Powers*, 201–203.

⁶ Vilmos Heiszler: *Az osztrák katonai vezetés és az Osztrák–Magyar Monarchia külpolitikája 1867–1882 között* (Budapest: Akadémiai Kiadó, 1984), 70-77.

⁷ Lajos Menyhárt, 'A három császár szövetsége és a magyar politikai közvélemény a keleti válság idején 1875–1878', *Acta Univ. Debrecensis. Series Historica* 5 (1966), 44.

as in the Cisleithanian legislative body, the *Reichsrat*.⁸ On the one hand, a pro-Russian policy could not only anger Hungarian public opinion but also with the victory of the Pan-Slavic movement could have had devastating effects on the integrity of the Monarchy. On the other hand, a strict anti-Russian policy could have endangered the alliance which provided the goodwill and alliance of the Monarchy's neighbours. To overcome these difficulties, on 31 December 1875, the so-called Andrassy Note was drafted, which contained a series of reforms for the rebellious principalities, without endangering the integrity of the Ottoman Empire. Ottoman leadership was desperate for a solution, as the state went bankrupt as early as October 1875, and creditors would not provide loans anymore.⁹ The integrity of the Empire therefore heavily depended on the goodwill and mediation of the bordering Great Powers.

Historiography, method and framework (foreign policy and frame analysis), limitations

The Great Eastern Crisis is a thoroughly discussed topic in historiography. From the range of books written on the British involvement in the affairs – such as the works of Seton-Watson, Harris, Millman, or Ković –, we can find several works on the history of Austro–Hungarian foreign affairs: G. H. Rupp examined the Austrian¹⁰ and Russian deals, István Diószegi studied German and Hungarian relations, and Rainer F. Schmidt discussed the failed alliance between Germany, Austria and England in his work.¹¹ However, these authors of the 20th century tended

⁸ József Zachar, *Az osztrák-német liberális Alkotmánypárt és a politikai hatalom: 1861-1881*, (Budapest: Akadémiai kiadó, 1981), 230-243.

⁹ Demeter, *Balkán kronológia*, 201.

¹⁰ In the case of the word *Austria* or *Austrian* the paper will employ the term to denote the Austro-Hungarian state or its leadership. As contemporary newspapers and diplomatic documents also rather use the term 'Austria' to refer to the entire state in diplomatic context, for the purpose of distinction I will use the historical concept of 'Cisleithania' or 'Cisleithanian Austria' to denote the territories of the Empire excluding the Hungarian Kingdom.

¹¹ R. W. Seton-Watson, *Disraeli, Gladstone, and the Eastern Question* (London: Macmillan & Co., 1935); David Harris, *A Diplomatic History of the Balkan Crisis of 1875–1878. The First Year* (Stanford: Stanford University Press, 1936); Richard Millman, *Britain and the Eastern Question. 1875–1878* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1979); Milos Ković, *Disraeli and the Eastern Question* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2011); George Hoover Rupp, *A Wavering Friendship. Russia and Austria 1876-1878* (Philadelphia: Porcupine Press, 1978); Diószegi, *Bismarck és Andrassy*; Rainer F. Schmidt, *Die gescheiterte Allianz: Österreich-Ungarn, England und das Deutsche Reich in der Ära Andrassy (1867 bis 1878/79)* (Frankfurt am Main: Peter Lang, 1992).

to adopt the viewpoint of a specific state, with little regard for different domestic factors of foreign policy. Therefore, by uncovering the motives behind the public opinion which have affected foreign policy, we aim to complement the existing literature on Austro-Hungarian state affairs.¹²

In the late days of October 1876, students took the streets in Budapest, while a couple of months later, in Britain, pro-government demonstrations occurred in London and other major cities. Later in 1878, Britain and Austria-Hungary closely cooperated to dismantle Russian gains in the Balkans and threatened Russia with Anglo-Austrian cooperation in an upcoming war.¹³ But if Austria was allied with Russia, how did these events occur in such a paralleled fashion, and what could have influenced Austrian decision-makers? The paper aims to examine how the narrative of the British bellicose media was adopted in leading Hungarian newspapers, and if it formulated domestic and foreign policies. Therefore the paper applies two methods: one to examine the discourses within leading Hungarian and British outlets, and the other one to help to interpret the findings of the former method on a policy level.

To observe the parallels between British and Hungarian political press the paper employs frame analysis. Framing refers to the process of how we organize our data, categorizing events, names and all other elements of a story, i.e. a narrative. Part of the process is to find certain discursive cues which would help identify certain patterns in explanations, solutions, context, types of language, definitions or labels, historical association, metaphors, and moral appeals.¹⁴ In the analysis, we identify British-originated news in Hungarian outlets (e.g. *Pesti Napló*, *Hon*,

¹² See: Menyhárt, 'A három császár szövetsége', 43-63; Tamás Sándor, *Tömegmegmozdulások Budapesten a dualizmus első évtizedeiben 1873–1903*, (PhD diss., Eötvös Loránd University, 2010).

¹³ Schmidt, *Die gescheiterte Allianz*, 383-420.

¹⁴ Jenny Kitzinger, 'Framing and Frame Analysis', in *Media Studies: Key Issues and Debates*, ed. Eoin Devereux (London: Sage Publishers, 2007), 134-161.

Ellenőr, Egyetértés), track it back to the source material – British press coverage of a certain event or article – and look for cues whether it adopted a similar view on the issue. The criteria of the selection of British and Hungarian news articles were the following: a.) there was an implicit or explicit reference to a British article, correspondence, telegram, parliamentary or other political speech in one or more of the indicated Hungarian newspapers, and b.) British news articles which mentioned Austria-Hungary in regard to the crisis or what agency it ought to have – even if it was not referenced in Hungarian outlets. The latter criterion highlights the limitation of the research. No matter the strive for an accurate historical account, we cannot for certain state that public opinion was influenced only by political articles and British agents of media alone, neither can we state that British opinion on Austria reached the public exclusively through the channels of Hungarian outlets. We have to consider that aside from the Hungarian journals, the public had other means of getting information: not only by different channels of information, but also through Viennese journals, and – judging by the sources in these news articles – German or French press and news agencies. Given the focus of the present study, we do not wish to discuss anything other than the influence of British media.

Secondly, the paper is centred around the greater issue of public pressure on foreign policy decision-making, therefore this paper applies Foreign Policy Analysis, which introduces media, interest groups and *public opinion* as independent factors in the process of policymaking.¹⁵ But what is public opinion? According to David L. Weakliem, the terminology appeared as early as the eighteenth century, but was first coined by Lord Russel in 1823: “it is fashion to point out increased and increasing influence of public opinion [...]”¹⁶ A more accurate account in Weakliem’s work is cited from Plamenatz,¹⁷ who states that public opinion is not necessarily

¹⁵ Marijke Breuning, *Foreign Policy Analysis* (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2007), 54-64, 120-123.

¹⁶ Quoted in David L. Weakliem, *Public Opinion* (Cambridge: Polity Press, 2020), 2.

¹⁷ John Plamenatz, ‘Public Opinion and Political Consciousness,’ *Political Studies* 29 (1975), 342-351.

the voice of the public, but rather the opinion outside governance and its hierarchy, yet close enough to it so that it can be acquired and have an indirect influence. Since the nineteenth century, with wider access to education, the public has become increasingly involved in politics and the media. The social disparity in this regard meant that while the elite, middle classes and certain groups could access newspapers and articulate their voice to a greater extent, other groups could mostly resort to resisting policies.¹⁸ There are different tools, such as the aforementioned *framing* and *priming* – the promotion of a certain topic – at the disposal of the political or media elite to determine and promote an agenda.¹⁹ The ground-breaking book of Walter Lippmann and the following debate concluded that public opinion appears as something not coherent, but rather volatile, and therefore cannot serve as a solid basis for policymaking.²⁰ Noam Chomsky and Edward S. Herman in their work dedicated to Lippmann argue that a so-called ‘propaganda model of communication’ is in effect. The authors claim that interpersonal relationships, ownership, advertising markets and license, the pre-selection of journalists and self-censorship all influence agenda-setting in favour of the elite. Meanwhile, the audience does not have the means to control the media, and in a centralised market, the propaganda model is more effective.²¹ This paper applies their thesis to theorise that the Hungarian public was largely influenced by the British political elite and the papers favouring the Tory Party. Although the aforementioned work mainly examines 20th-century cases and might raise some scepticism in the application of the theory in a nineteenth-century context, the work of Curran and Seaton referenced in the book also supports the thesis that monopoly ensured the control of the media

¹⁸ Weakliem, *Public opinion*, 2-4.

¹⁹ For further reference see: Patricia Moy, David Tewksbury, and Eike Mark Rinke, ‘Agenda-Setting, Priming, and Framing’, in *The International Encyclopaedia of Communication Theory and Philosophy*, edited by Jensen, K. B., Rothenbuler, E. W., Pooley, J. D. and Craig, R. T (Malden: Wiley & Blackwell, 2016), 1-13.

²⁰ Walter Lippmann, *Public Opinion* (New Brunswick, London: Transaction Publishers, [1922] 1998).

²¹ Edward S. Herman and Noam Chomsky, *Az Egyetértés-gépezet. A tömegmédiák politikai gazdaságtana* (Budapest: L’Harmattan, 2011). 13-20, 54-58.

for the elite as early as the middle of the nineteenth century.²² The elite domesticated the radical press of the 1840s, and by the 1860s, giant media enterprises ruled the market, which was also closely tied to political parties. It is not surprising that liberal politicians of the Gladstone era regarded media as an explicit means to control the sentiments of the public.²³ The scope of the present study involves the analysis of Hungarian news outlets. Among them the paper focuses particularly on those journals which do not belong to the group of official papers, and therefore do not act as the official mouthpiece of the government (such as *Pester Lloyd*), but rather as the carriers of public opinion. These Hungarian outlets researched are the *Pesti Napló*, *Hon*, *Ellenőr*, *Egyetértés*, and their understudied impact on foreign policy, as similar research on their Cisleithanian counterparts were already conducted, and as we will see the freedom of expression differed compared to the case of Hungary.²⁴

The role of the Hungarian press in Austro-Hungarian decision-making

As the wielder of the prerogative powers and a former absolutist ruler, the Austrian Emperor had all the means to control foreign policy. However, Franz Joseph did not solely make his decisions as he had a range of advisors – the military circle – and trusted Andrassy to handle foreign affairs.²⁵ The Habsburgs in the nineteenth century became increasingly aware of the power of the press as the Fourth Estate.²⁶ After losing to the Prussians at Sadowa in the fateful

²² James Curran and Jean Seaton, *Power without Responsibility. The Press and Broadcasting in Britain* (London, New York: Taylor and Francis, 1997).

²³ Curran and Seaton, *Power Without Responsibility*, 22-25, 39.

²⁴ Horst Haselsteiner, 'Öffentliche Meinung oder Meinungspluralität. Zum Widerhall der Okkupation in der Deutschsprachigen Presse der Donaumonarchie,' in *Otpor austrougarskoj okupaciji 1878*, eds Milorad Ekmečić (Sarajevo: Godine u Bosni i Hercegovini: naučni skup, 1978), 220-224, also see the work of Zachar, *Az osztrák-német liberális Alkotmánypárt*, who used the articles of the Viennese journal *Neue Freie Presse* to explore the influence of the Constitutional Party (*Verfassungspartei*) of German liberals in the legislative system of the Monarchy.

²⁵ Péter Hanák: 'Magyarország az Osztrák–Magyar Monarchiában. Túlsúly vagy függőség?', *Századok* 5 (1971), 928–929; Heiszler, *Az osztrák katonai vezetés*, 10-25, Éva Somogyi, *Magyarok a bécsi hivatalnoki világban. A közös külügyminisztérium magyar tisztviselői* (Budapest: MTA Bölcsészettudományi Kutatóközpont, Történettudományi Intézet, 2017), 32-37.

²⁶ Ágnes Deák and Ágnes Tamás, *Sziszifuszok küzdelme. Kormányzat és sajtópolitika Magyarországon 1860–1875* (Pécs: Kronosz Kiadó, 2021), 525-527.

year of 1866²⁷, and ceding the Empire's Western mission of uniting the Germans, for the sake of the integrity of the empire, the decision-makers of the newly established Austro-Hungarian Monarchy simply could no longer ignore the opinion of the public. Although the press played a crucial role in the Austro-Hungarian compromise (1867), as a minister of the Empire, Andrassy was very quick to apply the methods of his predecessors: in the press relations department of his bureau, he employed several secret agents as well as writers and middlemen (e.g. Mór Ludassi, Lajos Dóczy) to assert control over the media. His opinion, however, was that "as long as he enjoyed the confidence of the Emperor and delegations he would not need the press."²⁸ There is evidence that the department tried to influence British outlets: there are payslips for articles appearing in the *Daily Telegraph* and *Times*, but there is no information to what extent it worked.²⁹

Taking into account the difficulties and the initial expenses of a fresh newspaper, the costs of publicity were high in Austria-Hungary. Beyond the deposit and the colportage fee, the publishing market was carved up by limited companies (Athenaeum and Franklin Társulat) which were closely tied to the political elite.³⁰ Therefore, the press followed the division of political parties until 1875, after which the split and fusion of the old Deák Party³¹ resulted in the birth of the Liberal Party, *Pester Lloyd* – the semi-official organ edited by Miksa Falk –, and organs of the Left Centre opposition had to reposition themselves. The new premier Kálmán Tisza's mouthpiece was the small, but increasingly successful paper, *Ellenőr*. The journal *Hon*

²⁷ To commemorate the war and its consequences to German history, the year 1866 is often called the fateful year, or *Schicksalsjahr* in German. For further reference see Adam Wandruszka, *Schicksalsjahr 1866* (Koblenz: Styria Verlag, 1966).

²⁸ Deák and Tamás, *Sziszifuszok*, 98.

²⁹ Deák and Tamás, *Sziszifuszok*, 114, 559.

³⁰ Géza Buzinkay, *A magyar sajtó és újságírás története a kezdetektől a rendszerváltásig* (Budapest: Wolters Kluwer, 2016), 179–185, Deák and Tamás, *Sziszifuszok*, 90-99, 318-333.

³¹ The group of political elite loyal to their leader, Francis Deák (1803–1876), which favoured the Austro-Hungarian compromise and held key government positions in Hungary in the late 1860s and early 1870s.

– sometimes labelled as the ‘Hungarian version of the *Times*’ – remained close to the once critical governing party, as it was edited by the widely respected novelist/writer, Mór Jókai. While *Pesti Napló* – the original organ of the Deák Party – could keep liberal readers even after the fusion, *Pester Lloyd* remained an important source of foreign news, but it descended to the rank of official journals, therefore it falls out of the scope of the present study. Similar to the opposition mouthpiece *Egyetértés*, *Pesti Napló* could openly criticise the policy of the Monarchy. The former paper was most active in the years 1874–1878 and was the organ of the Centre-Left along with those of the former Hungarian Independence Party.³²

To further explain the scope of the research it is worth mentioning, why the research excluded the study of German-Austrian newspapers or the Viennese press. While in Cisleithania Austrian and Slavic press freedom was limited by the press laws of the absolutist era (the 1862 edicts), in Hungary, the laws of 1848 (Article XVIII) were enacted, and Hungary enjoyed a temporary era of press freedom of press.³³ Although it must be mentioned that the influence of media was limited by several factors. Only 6% of the population had the right to vote, while the share of literacy of the population had barely reached 40% by 1880.³⁴ Regardless of the constitutional boundaries of the Cisleithanian press, it is already claimed that the semi-official and rather liberal journals³⁵ tried to influence the foreign policy of the Empire. Their impact is well-documented in connection with Andrassy’s resignation, but their critique stemmed rather from the Eastern policy, than the adoption of foreign news sources. One if not the most significant among them was the organ of the German-liberals of the Constitutional Party, the *Neue Freie*

³² Buzinkay, *A magyar sajtó*, 201-204, 206-208.

³³ Buzinkay, *A magyar sajtó*, 180.

³⁴ László Katus, *A modern Magyarország születése. Magyarország története 1711–1914* (Pécs: Bocz Nyomdaipari Kft., 2012), 370, 519.

³⁵ Organs such as *Neue Freie Press*, *Morgenpost*, *Neues Wiener Journal*, *Neues Wiener Tagblatt*, *Wiener Allgemeine Zeitung*, *Die Presse*.

Presse, but Andrassy rather resigned over the wish of the Emperor and the objection of certain (liberal) political figureheads in the Cisleithanian government and delegations over his exposé concerning the occupation of Bosnia in 1879.³⁶ Hence, the focus lies on the examination of the earlier mentioned Hungarian papers, and not on the Cisleithanian press and political elite, which was mostly concerned over fiscal matters of the Bosnian occupation, months after our examined period.

British politics and press, 1875–1878

As British media outlets mirrored and magnetized domestic politics, a brief summary of British politics is necessary to understand the underlying divisions of newspapers and their standpoints. Politics in Britain in the 1870s were not only defined by the two great parties – the Conservative Party (the Tories) and the Liberal Party – but also by their leaders, Benjamin Disraeli (Lord Beaconsfield) and W. E. Gladstone. The ideas of these statesmen were greatly influenced by the decades of foreign policy under the Palmerston premiership which put the liberal-imperial policies to practice.³⁷ In 1876, upon defeating his rival, Gladstone, Disraeli became prime minister for a second time. After winning the Queen the title of Empress of India and earning her support (along with the title Earl of Lord Beaconsfield), he made his position exceptionally strong compared to his cabinet members. One of the victims of his growing power was his old political ally, Lord Derby. As a foreign secretary, he kept a diary and recorded his meetings with editors and other media figures.³⁸ Lord Derby was not the only minister who was removed from the government, as Disraeli shuffled his cabinet during the crisis. The Bulgarian atrocities

³⁶ Diószegi, *Bismarck és Andrassy*, 331-334; Horst Haselsteiner, 'Öffentliche Meinung oder Meinungspluralität. Zum Widerhall der Okkupation in der Deutschsprachigen Presse der Donaumonarchie', in *Otpor austrougarskoj okupaciji 1878*, ed. Milorad Ekmečić (Sarajevo: Godine u Bosni i Hercegovini: naučni skup, 1978), 220-233.

³⁷ Swartz, Marvin, *The Politics of British Foreign Policy in the era of Disraeli and Gladstone* (London: Macmillan, 1985), 12-23.

³⁸ Vincent, John, comp., *The Diaries of Edward Henry Stanley, 15th Earl of Derby (1826–1893). Between September 1869 and March 1878* (London: Offices of the Royal Historical Society, University College London, London, 1994).

voiced by the liberal opposition put the centre of attention on the Government and its treatment of its Ottoman ally; the controversies divided both public opinion and political parties.³⁹ By the summer of 1876, the Turkish frontier became increasingly important as Ottoman bashi-bazouk troops quenched the rebellious provinces and committed atrocities among civilians, and Serbia and Montenegro entered the war with Russian advisers in their ranks.⁴⁰ During the crisis, British ministers and other statesmen like Lord Salisbury and Lord Carnarvon were in favour of a Russian, Christian solution to the crisis. The differences lead to major shifts in the cabinet and both the Conservatives and the Liberal parties.⁴¹ As the Conservative government and cabinet had their divisions, the Liberals were split into camps of agitating ‘Gladstonian radicals’, and the more practical and commercial ‘pro-peace’ Whigs.⁴²

The bellicose media – and the Conservative Party supporting some papers with the help of Montague Corry⁴³, – incited anger as hundreds gathered in Hyde Park to protest. The expression ‘jingoists’ appeared during the last months of the crisis, denoting those who favoured Russophobic views and also those who backed heavy measures in foreign policy by supporting Lord Beaconsfield. Jingoism marked the polarization of the public, as Conservatives channelled anti-Russian sentiments to the working class under the banner of national interests.⁴⁴ On the topic of British public opinion, the early work of G. Carslake Thompson still provides a very detailed introduction to the media sphere of the era.⁴⁵ An outstanding paper was the *Daily*

³⁹ The Opposition and its leader, Gladstone have successfully campaigned with his pamphlet *The Bulgarian Horrors and the Question in the East in 1876* and in the Midlothian Campaign of 1879.

⁴⁰ Ković, *Disraeli*, 122.

⁴¹ In 1878 Salisbury replaced Derby, Hardy went to the House of Lords and F. A. Stanley (Derby’s brother) joined the cabinet as Secretary for War, and Hicks Beach had become Colonial Secretary after the resignation of Carnarvon (Swartz, *Politics*, 85).

⁴² Ković, *Disraeli*, 84; Swartz, *Politics*, 40-41, 74-75.

⁴³ The secretary of the prime minister, in office 1874–1880.

⁴⁴ Carslake George Thompson, *Public Opinion and Lord Beaconsfield 1875–1880*, vol I. (London: Macmillan and Co., 1886), 52-59.

⁴⁵ Although Thompson has sound observations, his categorisation is admittedly biased (Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 72-170).

Telegraph, which became the ‘Tory-Mahometan’ paper, but despite the label, it remained a popular outlet.⁴⁶ Newspapers either supported the peace argument (*Daily News*) or pursued sensation and the involvement of the public in the affair. The *Pall Mall Gazette* (*P.M.G.*), the *Standard* (alternatively *London Evening Standard*), *Spectator* and the *Globe* belonged to the latter group.⁴⁷ One of the most reliable and impartial newspapers was *The Times*. Despite that the manager, J. C. MacDonald admittedly sympathized with Russians, the owner, John Walter and editor J. T. Delane were not committed to leading an ‘anti-Turkish’ paper.⁴⁸

British pro-Turkish and anti-Russian sentiments in Hungarian outlets

After the outbreak of the Herzegovinian revolts in the summer of 1875, Hungarian outlets initially remained calm and featured British articles in the usual manner as they did ever since the early nineteenth century.⁴⁹ University students, however, became increasingly active, mostly in answering to the governing party abandoning its earlier vision of an independent Hungary.⁵⁰ In Britain, the majority of the British Press was pro-Ottoman, and pro-status quo in the very beginning. In August the *Spectator* and *Times* published pro-peace articles with some humanitarian arguments, very much inspired by Greek supporter Liberals such as Lord Russell.⁵¹ By September 17, the *Times* mentioned that there could be Russian involvement behind the uprisings.⁵² Other papers estimated the dangerous possibility of Turkey conceding territories to Russia.⁵³ By November 1, the *Daily News* took an anti-Turkish stance, but other British organs were appalled by Russian diplomatic manoeuvres which left the line of reform

⁴⁶ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 435-440.

⁴⁷ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 432; Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 246, 250-254.

⁴⁸ Swartz, *Politics*, 40.

⁴⁹ András Döbör, *Sajtópolitika és politikai sajtó Magyarországon (1780–1840)* (Budapest: Gondolat Kiadó, 2018), 188-190.

⁵⁰ Sándor, *Tömegmozdulások*, 81-82.

⁵¹ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 217-224, *Spectator*, August 21, 1875, 1, *Times*, “The Herzegovina,” August 21, 1875, 6.

⁵² *Times*, “Herzegovina,” September 17, 1875, 5.

⁵³ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 225-231.

in favour of armed intervention.⁵⁴ *Times* and *P.M.G.* warned about Russian intentions, and also some theories appeared in the *Times* that Austria was willing to occupy Turkish provinces.⁵⁵ Also later that month Disraeli held his Guildhall speech, which implied British involvement.⁵⁶

In Hungarian papers, the main organ of the opposition, *Egyetértés* was eager to feature pro-Turkish articles in the *Daily Telegraph* and the *Standard*.⁵⁷ The turning point however came much later in the autumn of the next year, when the Hungarian press started to feature a number of articles from the British conservative press in the heat of Gladstone's atrocity campaign.

In January 1876, as the Great Powers joined the Andrassy Note, *Pesti Napló* voiced the necessity of joint action of the Three Emperors for a peaceful solution, while other papers deterred from pacifism. The opposition adopted a Russophobe view, but would not press the matter, as the government paper, *Ellenőr* in its February 15 issue called out Russia as the perpetrator behind the events in the Balkans.⁵⁸ At the same time, British outlets were mostly proposing peace: *Times* and *Daily Telegraph* emphasised how Britain was in favour of all points of the Austrian proposal.⁵⁹ Concerning the Hungarian papers, *Hon* published statements of English MPs and referenced the *Times* on Andrassy's reform plans.⁶⁰ At the end of the articles, general references were made to England's disposition to war. Although England was criticised in the paper, it was presented as Andrassy's partner in a possible 'eastern action'.⁶¹ In Britain by March, both liberal and conservative organs of the British Press stated that the Andrassy Note

⁵⁴ *Daily News*, November 1, 1875.

⁵⁵ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 231-233, 243-255; *Times*, "Pan-Sclavonia," October 20, 1875, 4; *Times*, "Turkey," November 5, 1875, 5; *Times*, "The Eastern Question," December 1, 1875, 5; *P.M.G.*, "The European Prospect today," November 9, 1875, 1.

⁵⁶ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 235-236.

⁵⁷ *Egyetértés* issues October 13-15, 1875 and December 29, 1875, 1-4.

⁵⁸ Menyhárt, 'A három császár', 48.

⁵⁹ *Times*, "Count Andrassy's Note," January 27, 1876, 5. *Daily Telegraph*, January 17, 1876, 4.

⁶⁰ *Times*, "Count Andrassy's Note," January 20, 1876, 9.

⁶¹ *Hon*, January 24, 1876, 1.

has failed.⁶² British organs at the time were very dismayed by Austrian diplomacy and approved the rejection of the note by the British government. The Berlin Memorandum was even denounced as “[...] Austrian in principle, Russian in detail”⁶³ in the *Times*, and by June it went as far as to announce Britain as the only leading power to resolve the conflict.⁶⁴ Hungarian readers, however, could only read a filtered, different attitude in the papers. Therefore, the rejection of the note was portrayed as a call for an alliance. In its June 2 issue, the *Hon* considered the chances of British intervention and cited the *Observer* as it contrasted Britain with Russia. Also in the June 6 and 9 issues, it wrote on the new political direction of England and the Monarchy, and with the new Turkish ruler's accession to the throne a possible decisive action: “[...] but the fact is that it is in England's interest to isolate Russia [...] the fact is also that with an Eastern policy conducted in the English spirit the interests of our Monarchy are more certainly safeguarded [...]”⁶⁵ Further in June, the paper featured Disraeli's speeches. In the July 19 issue, the *Pesti Napló* also contemplated the chances of war and it was sceptical about the prospect of a settlement.⁶⁶

Starting from early June to September, *Times* published a great number of articles on the Bulgarian atrocities and set the agenda for all papers in the coming months.⁶⁷ In its June 9 issue, the *Hon* cited the *Times* and other London news sources.⁶⁸ In its June 30 issue, the *Hon* did a special feature on the Eastern Question and reports of British arms shipments, while also providing the readers with a multi-episode historical essay on the topic.⁶⁹ In the June issues of

⁶² Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I. 278-280; *Times*, “Invasion of Bosnia,” April 18, 1876, 7; *P.M.G.*, “The Eastern Question,” April 17, 1876, 1.

⁶³ *Times*, “The Berlin Conference,” May 23, 1876, 9.

⁶⁴ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 289.

⁶⁵ *Hon*, June 6, 1876, 1.

⁶⁶ Menyhárt, ‘A három császár’, 49-50.

⁶⁷ *Times*, “Atrocities in Bulgaria,” August 8, 1876, 5; *Times*, “Turkish Atrocities,” September 6, 1876, 8.

⁶⁸ *Hon*, June 9, 1876, 1; *Times*, “The Eastern Question,” June 9, 1876, 9.

⁶⁹ *Hon*, June 30, 1876, 1.

Ellenőr, the paper speculated a British involvement in a war against Russia and carried reports from English and 'warmongering' German newspapers.⁷⁰ *Pesti Napló* wrote about the infiltration of pan-Slavism into European public opinion, which it attributed to the Russian ties with the Monarchy.⁷¹ It was the point when the rumours of the May atrocities began to sink into the Hungarian press with a few weeks of delay. In Britain, *P.M.G.* suggested that 'humanitarians mislead' since they misjudged the actions of Turkey which sought integrity.⁷² Meanwhile, the *Daily News* criticised Disraeli and the Government and went on the offensive in its June 23 and July 8 issues.⁷³ To avoid damage, Derby communicated to the Constantinople ambassador, that he should do all in his power to stop the Porte and the possible outrage – *Daily News* and *Times* published Derby's despatch and later admired it.⁷⁴ These Blue Books were published in the *Times*, but the papers condemned the slaughter and portrayed Disraeli and Derby as responsible.⁷⁵ *Daily Telegraph* and *P.M.G.* started to build a narrative against the humanitarians to protect Derby's policy.⁷⁶

In the following months the pressure mounted on Andrassy, and the *Egyetértés* regained its pro-Turkish stance. The newspaper began to emphasise a narrative that Germany would certainly support the Hungarians in the event of a Russian-Hungarian conflict.⁷⁷ From the autumn of 1876 onwards, *Ellenőr* devoted a special 'Eastern War' column to the reports of the British and German news agencies, and during Andrassy's visit to Budapest, it published a particularly large number of articles on the topic of war. In its issue of September 7, 1876, it reported on the

⁷⁰ *Ellenőr*, June 1-2, 7-9, 19, 23 issues, 1876.

⁷¹ Menyhárt, 'A három császár', 50-51.

⁷² Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 293-294.

⁷³ *Daily News*, June 23, 1876, 5; Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 310-313.

⁷⁴ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 342-344; *Daily News*, August 12, 1876, 5.

⁷⁵ *Times*, "The Affairs of Turkey," July 22, 1876, 10; Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 316-317.

⁷⁶ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 303-305, 336-337; *Daily Telegraph*, June 30, 1876; *P.M.G.*, "The Policy of the Government in the East," June 24, 1876, 1; *Daily Telegraph*, July 18, 1876, 4-5.

⁷⁷ Menyhárt, 'A három császár', 52, 60.

change in English public opinion following the atrocities agitation “In England, agitation against Turkish atrocities is on the rise”).⁷⁸ In its September 10 issue, the paper goes as far as to call the agitation “philanthropy and Russophile rumble degraded to party manoeuvres.”⁷⁹ The same issue concluded its foreign affairs column with reviews of Gladstone's pamphlet in the *Morning Post*, *Daily Telegraph* and *Standard*.⁸⁰ In their quest for readership, the editors published a certain Mr H. Brown's anxious letters to Hungarians on the front page, which commented on Gladstone's protests, and at the same time discussed Hungarian policy, public opinion, and a desirable Turkish victory.⁸¹ The *Pesti Napló* also featured the events of the Serbian-Turkish war on the front page, but in its September 11 issue, it also presented Gladstone's speeches.⁸² On September 15, the *Daily Telegraph's* comment on ‘sickening humanitarianism’ was also featured in translation.⁸³ The mentions of Austrian-British cooperation continued in both countries’ media. In the September 29 issue, the *Times* commented on the atrocities and also claimed that if Austria was unwilling, it is up to Britain to keep order in the Balkans.⁸⁴ Also some anti-Russian sentiments – an article by the Bishop of Exeter – appeared in the *Times* by mid-September but the only paper was still *Daily Telegraph* which vehemently defended the government's position.⁸⁵ The turning point however seems to be the Aylesbury speech (September 20) of Disraeli. This is the speech that has most likely connected the anti-Russian feelings of Hungarian newsreaders and the pro-Turkish sentiments of the British conservative media.⁸⁶ The *Daily News* and the *Spectator* considered it catastrophic, while the *Times* generally approved it. The speech surprisingly revived the pro-

⁷⁸ *Ellenőr*, issues September 7, 1876, and October 13, 1876.

⁷⁹ *Ellenőr*, September 10, 1876, 1.

⁸⁰ *Ellenőr*, September 10, 1876, 1.

⁸¹ *Ellenőr*, issues September 11-24, 1876.

⁸² *Pesti Napló*, September 11, 1876, 1.

⁸³ *Pesti Napló*, September 15, 1876, 1.

⁸⁴ *Times*, “Eastern Question,” September 29, 1876, 4.

⁸⁵ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I.: 413, 432-435.

⁸⁶ *Egyetértés* welcomed and featured Disraeli's speech in a long lead in its September 25, 1876 issue (1-4).

Turkish voices in the country and discouraged the liberal camp.⁸⁷ In early October, Derby was outlined as a competent leader by the *Daily Telegraph* and *P.M.G.*. The papers tried to sell his idea, a modified memorandum called the ‘English Terms’, and also claimed that humanitarian attitude is the path of “national destruction”.⁸⁸ The *Times* criticised Derby but mentioned Austria and her possible move to occupy Bosnia in accordance with Russia.⁸⁹ Articles of both sides of the argument appeared in these papers, as Gladstone’s agitation continued throughout the month.⁹⁰ While *Daily News* and *Times* rekindled the humanitarian agitation, the *Spectator* in its October 21 issue wrote on how Austria seems inclined to join Russia in sharing the spoils: the only thing preventing them was the agitation.⁹¹ The Aylesbury speech also inspired *Egyetértés*, which blamed Gladstone and humanitarians for a pro-Russian attitude. The paper could identify more with Conservative goals, and therefore cited the *Daily Telegraph*.⁹²

In late October, *Pesti Napló* competed with the pro-government Viennese press in reporting news about a possible British or German alliance and criticised the *Times* for endorsing the pro-Russian demonstrations in Britain.⁹³ On October 9, *Times* disclosed a lengthy speech from W. E. Forster. In the speech the inaction of Austria is mentioned: “We cannot expect Hungary or Austria or any subject of the Austrian Empire, quietly to submit to Russia taking possession of the Lower Danube.”⁹⁴ *Ellenőr* adopted these tones of the English press, and in the later issues it quoted articles from the *Times*, *Telegraph* and German press, and despite being a government

⁸⁷ Carslake George Thompson, *Public Opinion and Lord Beaconsfield 1875–1880*, vol II. (London: Macmillan and Co., 1886), 19–39; *Daily News*, September 21, 1876, 5; *Spectator*, September 23, 1876, 1; *Times*, “Mr. Gladstone and the Party,” September 26, 1876, 8.

⁸⁸ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 50–67, 77; *Daily Telegraph*, “The Bulgarian Massacres,” October 7, 1876, 5; *P.M.G.*, “The Porte and the English Proposals,” October 3, 1876, 9.

⁸⁹ *Times*, “Russia and Austria,” October 3, 1876, 8.

⁹⁰ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 71–81.

⁹¹ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 83; *Spectator*, October 21, 1876, 1.

⁹² *Egyetértés*, September 10, 11, 14, 19, 20 issues, 1876.

⁹³ *Pesti Napló*, October 20, 1876, 1.

⁹⁴ *Times*, “The Eastern Question,” October 9, 1876, 10.

paper, also criticised Hungarian inaction.⁹⁵ In its October 22 issue, the paper featured an article where students called for action:

To the students of the two universities [of Budapest]! The public of the nation has chosen. Hungarians cannot remain indebted to their Turkish neighbours. The progress and freedom of Europe are threatened by a disaster; the horror of the Siberian lead mines, the perpetrator of the Warsaw atrocities is trampling international rights, under the guise of the "bloody cross", while threatening the tranquillity of Europe and its protector, Hungary. [...] Let us show that the brotherly Turkish nation is accompanied in its bloody struggles by the sympathy of the Hungarian youth. [...] To express our sympathy for the Turkish nation, we will organize a torchlight procession [...].⁹⁶

On 21 October and the large gathering of individuals was reported in great detail in all of the Hungarian press. After the rally, a delegation of 18 people visited the Hungarian premier who – although he would not ban it – asked the students to postpone the march.⁹⁷ A reflection on the British press coverage can be seen in the Prime Minister's words to the students: “If you follow closely the foreign press, you must know, that the Hungarian nation will be placed in front of the world [...] as one which wishes to oppress the Eastern Christians, and therefore people like Gladstone may utter that the Hungarian race must be swept from the face of the Earth [...]”.⁹⁸ Overnight, the demonstrators became a mixed crowd of the bourgeoisie and workers of Budapest. Escorted by the police, they made their way to the house of the editor of *Hon*, Jókai, who, although had the intention of appeasing the protesters, did not join them.⁹⁹ Later, the crowd split and a small number of them marched to the Turkish consul's apartment, where they were dispersed by the police.¹⁰⁰ Later, students wanted to publish their proclamations in the ‘foreign press’, and in the October 28 issue of *Egyetértés*, *Times* and *Spectator* articles were also featured supporting the idea of dishonest Russian diplomacy. In these late October issues,

⁹⁵ *Ellenőr*, October 17, 1876, 1.

⁹⁶ *Ellenőr*, October 22, 1876, 1.

⁹⁷ Sándor, *Tömegmegmozdulások*, 84.

⁹⁸ *Pesti Napló*, October 23, 1876, 1; *Egyetértés* October 24, 1876, 1-4.

⁹⁹ Sándor, *Tömegmegmozdulások*, 86–87.

¹⁰⁰ *Ellenőr*, October 27, 1876, 1.

the paper also claimed that Andrassy was now in a difficult position as the *Reichsrat* considered limiting the powers of the ministry.¹⁰¹ Later in November the *Standard* also reinforced these notions.¹⁰² Although the paper for a short period was preoccupied with the publication of Lajos Kossuth's ideas on the Eastern Question and the necessity of a preventive war¹⁰³, the paper also wanted to make the audience believe in British participation. "England is prepared [...] and will fight until justice shall be done [...]"¹⁰⁴ Also around the same time, Beaconsfield addressed his Guildhall speech (November 9) to the audience of the Lord Mayor's banquet, shortly after the Tsar addressed his Moscow speech to his subjects. The tory press and the *Standard* connected the two speeches, and interpreted them as a hostile dialogue between the British premier and the Russian Tsar.¹⁰⁵ *Egyetértés* also featured the speech in full length in its November 14 issue.¹⁰⁶ Starting from mid-November, the bellicose party in England was on the rise. The *Daily News* remained critical of Beaconsfield and added that he would never convince Austria to go against Russia, but also admitted that the speech of the Tsar was a break with Derby's peaceful efforts.¹⁰⁷ These notions along with others were also featured in *Hon.*¹⁰⁸ *Egyetértés* and *Hon* started to cite the information gathered by *P.M.G.* and *Daily Telegraph* on Russian troops.¹⁰⁹ In the next year, from February until May 1877 the British public calmed down, and resorted to an observant mode throughout the conference period, as the readers were apparently more interested in diplomacy.¹¹⁰

¹⁰¹ *Egyetértés* issues October 26-31, 1876; *Times*, "The Eastern Question," October 21, 1876, 5; *Times*, "The Crisis," October 21, 1876, 9.

¹⁰² *Egyetértés* issues November 4, 7, 1876; *Standard*, "Count Andrassy," November 10, 1876, 5.

¹⁰³ *Egyetértés* issues November 5, 11, 25, 1876, 1-4.

¹⁰⁴ *Egyetértés* November 11, 1876, 1-4.

¹⁰⁵ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 93-107; also the lead article in *Standard*, November 10, 1876, 4.

¹⁰⁶ *Egyetértés*, November 14, 1876, 1-4.

¹⁰⁷ *Daily News*, November 25, 1876, 4.

¹⁰⁸ *Hon*, issues November 11, 14, 1876.

¹⁰⁹ *Egyetértés*, November 19, 1876, 1-4; *Hon*, November 26, 1876, 1; *P.M.G.*, "The Situation in Europe," November 17, 1876, 5.

¹¹⁰ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 128, 142-165.

In Hungary, from the end of 1876 onwards, part of the governing party, the opposition, and their press, associated Austro-Hungarian foreign policy failures with a dangerous Russian alliance. In the Hungarian parliament, MPs, like Lajos Mocsáry and Ignác Helfy denounced Tisza's illegal police orders in their interpellations and Beaconsfield's speech was used against the prime minister during a debate.¹¹¹ During the Spring of 1877, the students collected a great sum of donations and had a ceremonial sword made for Abdul Kerim, which they took to Constantinople, representing the goodwill of the Hungarian people in a semi-official capacity.¹¹² To deter this political fiasco, Tisza asked Andrassy in a lengthy letter to dissuade the students.¹¹³ The Hungarian premier however also successfully persuaded the Emperor to not apply stricter measures against the returning students as it would have an adversary effect on stability.¹¹⁴

During the Conference of Constantinople (December 23, 1876 – January 20, 1877), the *Daily Telegraph* committed itself to comment on Salisbury's mission and almost to instruct the British envoy, while also deeming Turkish reforms as the sufficient means to oppose Russia.¹¹⁵ In their February issues *Pesti Napló*, *Ellenőr* and *Egyetértés* featured the speeches of British conservatives and transcripts from the House of Commons.¹¹⁶ After the Russo-Turkish War broke out on April 24, 1877, the *Daily Telegraph* claimed that the Russian aim was to occupy the capital and therefore violate European and British interests.¹¹⁷ With British and Austrian interests aligning, on May 5 a full article was written in the *Times* on Austrian neutrality.¹¹⁸ Also a few days later, letters of a certain 'Anglophil' were published in the *Daily Telegraph*

¹¹¹ *Egyetértés*, November 26, 1876, 1-4.

¹¹² Sándor, *Tömegmegmozdulások*, 92-93.

¹¹³ HU-MNL, X, PA X689, 1794, 103. Kálmán Tisza to Gyula Andrassy, January 3, 1877.

¹¹⁴ HU-MNL-OL-P 4-(592), Kálmán Tisza to Emperor Franz Joseph, August 22, 1877.

¹¹⁵ *The Daily Telegraph*, January 6, 1877, 4-5.

¹¹⁶ *Egyetértés*, issues February 17, 18, 20, 1877, 1-4; *Ellenőr*, February 18, 1877, 1-2.

¹¹⁷ Thompson, *Public opinion* vol. II., 184-185; *The Daily Telegraph*, issues April 27-30, 1877, 4-5.

¹¹⁸ *Times*, "Austria," May 5, 1877, 7.

and advocated for Britain to join Austria and Turkey against the Russians.¹¹⁹ We do not know the author of the latter article, but this is the time when secret talks between Andrassy and Lord Beaconsfield began.¹²⁰ During these weeks, *Times* also published an unusually large number of articles on Austria.¹²¹ In the Hungarian press, these notions also appeared in May, and some Hungarian politicians even advocated for an immediate military alliance with Britain.¹²² Furthermore, the *Daily Telegraph* and *Spectator* believed that if Britain did not intervene, the fleet and the country would lose prestige.¹²³

Articles in the *Pesti Napló* and *Egyetértés* criticised the loss of sovereignty of Hungarian foreign policy. Tisza's speech on July 1 reassured his party, and then, relying on information from Andrassy, he claimed that the Monarchy would not rule out the partition of Turkish territories in the Balkans. The parliament was then dissolved before the dispute could escalate. *Pesti Napló* published articles until 1878 quoting statements by opposition MPs who portrayed a pro-Russian policy as 'unnatural' and 'a prison' for Hungarians. With the occupation of Bosnia being floated, the voice of the Hungarian press became threatening.¹²⁴ After the October 15 defeat of the Ottoman forces, liberal voices of *Daily News* also assumed a possible British military intervention if Russians were to overwhelm Constantinople.¹²⁵ Now the pro-Turkish pressure was mounting on the government. In early November, Disraeli reinforced his support of his bellicose voters and condemned Liberals.¹²⁶ *Egyetértés*, *Ellenőr*, and the rest of the Hungarian press relied on their own correspondents for a few months, but later the opposition paper

¹¹⁹ Thompson, *Public opinion* vol. II., 186; *The Daily Telegraph*, May 15, 1877, 5.

¹²⁰ István Diószegi, 'Andrassy und Disraeli im Sommer des Jahres 1877', *Studia Historica Academiae Scientiarum Hungaricae* 156 (1980), <http://real-eod.mtak.hu/10997/>, accessed August 02, 2022.

¹²¹ *Times* "The War" and "Austrian Neutrality" articles in issues May 16, and June 2, 5, 14, 21, 25, 29, 1877.

¹²² *Hon*, May 7, 1877, 1; *Egyetértés*, May 17, 1877, 1-4; *Ellenőr*, issues May 20-22, 1877.

¹²³ Thompson, *Public opinion* vol. II., 250-254; *The Daily Telegraph*, "British Troops for the East," July 25, 1877, 5; *Spectator*, August 18, 1877, 1.

¹²⁴ Menyhárt, 'A három császár', 52-60.

¹²⁵ *Daily News*, November 21, 1877, 5.

¹²⁶ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 262-265.

admitted the Turkish defeat, while also referencing the *Daily Telegraph* to cover the issue.¹²⁷ It became clear that moderates like Derby were overwhelmed by the bellicose party. With the fall of Plevna on December 10, the pro-Turkish media were of the opinion that conference and mediation is reasonable, but from mid-January 1878, war was also on the table.¹²⁸ *Egyetértés* featured a variety of articles from the *Times*, *Daily Telegraph*, and *Morning Post* and also saw mediation as fitting.¹²⁹ Later the paper called out *Times* as an opposition mouthpiece, one which supports “the bloodthirsty philanthropists”.¹³⁰ In its December 26 issue, the *Times* alluded that the British government was ready for war and turned to the policy of armed neutrality. In early January, the *Daily News* also communicated the notion, that at some point England ‘must’ join the war on their side.¹³¹ The *Standard* reinforced the idea, while the *Globe* (December 19 issue) speculated that Russians would force Turkey to accept peace on their terms.¹³² Russophobe, pro-government working men’s associations came to the forefront, as even the Liberal Party itself became divided concerning the issue of the straits. British anti-Russian protesters met on December 29, in Trafalgar Square. As the event was announced by the *Times* issue of the same day, two days later, self-proclaimed “Turkish friends” in Hungary – mainly Hungarian opposition politicians, like Ignác Helfy and Lajos Simonyi – sent their ‘sympathetic greetings’ from Budapest via the *Times*.¹³³ Shortly after the exchange, *Egyetértés* featured news from *Times*, *P.M.G.*, *Daily News*, *Daily Telegraph* and *Standard* articles.¹³⁴ *Hon* also reported on the British domestic events with great excitement.¹³⁵ For a brief moment, it seemed that Britain was united under the banner of intervention, but on January 2, Lord Carnarvon’s speech

¹²⁷ See *Ellenőr*, issues October 16, 20, 1877; *Egyetértés*, November 19, 1877, 1-4; *The Daily Telegraph*, November 17, 1877, 5.

¹²⁸ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 266-267.

¹²⁹ *Egyetértés*, December 12, 1877, 1-4.

¹³⁰ *Egyetértés*, December 25, 1877. 1-4.

¹³¹ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 270-273; *Daily News*, issues January 2-3, 1878.

¹³² Lead article in *Standard*, December 20, 1877, 4,

¹³³ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 290-291.

¹³⁴ *Egyetértés*, December 31, 1877, 1-4; also a similar feature in the next issue January 1, 1877, 2-3.

¹³⁵ *Hon*, issues December 28–31, 1877.

dissuaded the jingoes.¹³⁶ After the first sitting of Parliament, Beaconsfield stated in his speech that there was no need for the Andrassy Note or the involvement of the Great Powers, as the English neutral stance was deliberate, and Britain would be able to defend its interests with or without allies.¹³⁷ This was also possibly a message for Andrassy, who, according to *Egyetértés* was now under heavy pressure from the Vienna circles as the *Pester Lloyd* officially took his side.¹³⁸ There were also *Times* articles in early January which suggested Austro-British cooperation.¹³⁹ *Egyetértés* published more articles on the possibility of Britain entering the conflict.¹⁴⁰ As the paper eagerly reported on the sailing of the British fleet near the conflict, it also criticised the inaction of Austria until the end of the month.¹⁴¹ The notion of alliance returns much later, after the one-sided preliminary peace efforts imposed by Russia on Turkey.¹⁴² Lastly, the alliance is mentioned by the *Times* before Britain and Austria secretly agreed on their terms of what policy to follow in the Balkans.¹⁴³

Conclusion – Political consequences in Austria–Hungary. The effect of British tory newspapers

Although there is no direct evidence to connect the Hungarian public and the opinions expressed in the press, as Hungarian newspapers adopted the articles of the British conservative press, unrest followed in the Dual Monarchy. This may have been due to the fact that the major Austrian and Hungarian news agencies were only established during the crisis, and papers of the Monarchy could rely only on agencies such as Havas, Reuters and Times, and to some extent articles in German/Viennese newspapers.¹⁴⁴ The editor of *Egyetértés* in the November

¹³⁶ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 294-295; *Daily News*, January 3, 1878, 3.

¹³⁷ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 300-301.

¹³⁸ *Egyetértés*, January 3, 1878.

¹³⁹ *Times*, “Armistice Negotiations,” January 14-15, 1878, 5; *Times*, “The War and Peace Negotiations,” January 21, 1878, 9.

¹⁴⁰ *Egyetértés*, issues January 9-12, 1878.

¹⁴¹ *Egyetértés*, issues January 14, 17, 20, 1878.

¹⁴² *Times*, “The Eastern Question,” March 14, 1878, 9.

¹⁴³ *Times*, issues May 31, June 1-3, 1878, on the matter of the agreement see: William A. Gould, ‘The Anglo-Austrian Agreement of 1878’, *English Historical Review*, (1926), 108-112.

¹⁴⁴ Buzinkay, *A magyar sajtó*, 185-186.

11, 1875 issue even indicates that the English press had correspondents all over the Balkans, which Austro–Hungarian papers could afford only much later.¹⁴⁵ By adopting the British news of the crisis in the East, they also 'imported' the political narrative of British outlets and what was inspired by the Conservative Party elite. By fitting it to their anti-Russian view, the agenda was set for the press in both pro-government and opposition papers in Hungary. In line with Herman and Chomsky's concept, the idea that the adopted agenda shaped the 'position' of public opinion is consistent. Despite the fact that press support was an established tool to control the press in the Monarchy, Hungarian outlets departed considerably from the line that would have been comfortable for the decision-makers and caused a major political crisis. The aforementioned is most notable in the case of *Egyetértés* and its adoption of a bellicose narrative from *The Daily Telegraph*, but at some point during the crisis, both the opposition and the government press criticised the seemingly passive Austro-Hungarian foreign policy. Similar to the Midlothian campaign that led to the Liberal Party's victory in British politics, the Eastern Question had upset the 1878 elections in Hungary, and the Tisza regime was shaken when the party lost 100 seats in the legislature.¹⁴⁶ The pressure of the Hungarian public and attitude also had a direct effect when Andrassy and Tisza cast their vote in the January 14-15, 1878 Imperial War Council. The spectacular expressions of Hungarian public opinion were used in their arguments as they tried to justify the idea of a preventive war against Russia, instead of the occupation of Bosnia. In the end, Franz Joseph and the military circle advised Andrassy to rather prepare for the peace talks – later known as the Berlin Congress of 1878.¹⁴⁷

¹⁴⁵ *Egyetértés*, November 11, 1875.

¹⁴⁶ Katus, *A modern Magyarország születése*, 362-363.

¹⁴⁷ László Bencze, *Bosznia és Hercegovina okkupációja 1878-ban* (Budapest: Akadémiai Kiadó, 1987), 44-49.

In 1878, the Austro-Hungarian leadership and the influential military circles had to reckon with two consequences of the anti-Russian/pro-Turkish narrative in Hungarian public opinion. Firstly, public opposition in Cisleithania, which opposed the Monarchy's military action because of the expected costs. Secondly Andrassy, the former national hero – praised by Deák as the miraculous statesman – had earned the disapproval of the Hungarian public who, instead of a war in the East, faced the occupation of Bosnia, against the realm of the ‘brotherly’ Turkish people. A year later in 1879, Andrassy resigned, and in an undated document, he tells us that the press should not have judged him so harshly, because “a minister bears his only duty [...] to history itself. [...] If a minister lets things go their own way [...] both halves of the Monarchy are united in the joy that nothing really happens. And then the press and the delegates are perfectly content”.¹⁴⁸

¹⁴⁸ HU-MNL-OL-P 4-(592), Note 33.

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Ellenőr 1875–1878

A Hon 1875–1878

Pesti Napló 1875–1878

Országos Széchenyi Könyvtár

Egyetértés 1875–1878

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